

Reliability of APACHE II and Sofa Scoring System in Assessing the Outcomes in ICU Patients with Sepsis and MODS– A Cross-Sectional Study

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Abstract:

Introduction: Sepsis and multi-organ failure arising from it are among the leading cause of death in patients admitted to the intensive care unit. Several scoring systems have been formulated to assess the severity of illness and provide the prognostic information to the treating physician for critically ill patients in medical intensive care unit (ICU). These severity scores help orient the limited resources towards more suitable patients. However, no consensus has been established regarding the superiority of the scoring system. APACHE (acute physiology age chronic health evaluation) and SOFA (sequential organ failure assessment) scores are the widely used scoring systems to predict the clinical outcome of critically ill patients in the ICU.

Objective: To compare and determine the reliability of APACHE II and SOFA scoring system in predicting the clinical outcome in terms of mortality or survival in ICU patients with sepsis with MODS.

Methodology: The present observational study was carried out in medicine intensive care unit at a tertiary care center involving 60 cases of sepsis.

Results: Mean APACHE II score in survivors was 16.81±4.52 and in non survivors was 25.63±5.78. we compared the APACHE II score between two groups and found that the difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Mean APACHE II score in survivors was 16.81±4.52 and in non survivors was 25.63±5.78. we compared the APACHE II score between two groups and found that the difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). The p value was found to be significant. Hence a higher mean SOFA score indicates a higher probability of mortality.

Conclusion: Both the APACHE II score and SOFA scores were noted to have significant correlation with mortality in cases of sepsis – multi organ dysfunction syndrome. Higher values of APACHE 2, SOFA scores were associated with higher mortality.

Keywords: APACHE II, SOFA, sepsis, MODS.

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Introduction

Sepsis and multi-organ failure arising from it are among the leading cause of death in patients admitted to the intensive care unit. Several scoring systems have been formulated to assess the severity of illness and provide the prognostic information to the treating physician for critically ill patients in medical intensive care unit (ICU).

These severity scores help orient the limited resources towards more suitable patients. However, no consensus has been established regarding the superiority of the scoring system. [1,2] APACHE

(acute physiology age chronic health evaluation) and SOFA (sequential organ failure assessment) scores are the widely used scoring systems to predict the clinical outcome of critically ill patients in the ICU. APACHE was first introduced in 1981 by William Knaus and colleagues at George Washington Medical University as a system for classifying the disease severity in acutely ill patients using 12 physiological, objective and numerical variables within 24 hours of ICU admission. [3]

The Sequential Organ Failure Assessment (SOFA)

score was introduced as a simple objective score in 1994. It quantifies the severity of organ dysfunction in six organ systems: respiratory, circulatory, renal, hematology, hepatic and central nervous system and the function and dysfunction is graded from 0-4. [4] Although SOFA was developed to quantify organ dysfunction, it has been demonstrated in several studies to predict mortality and morbidity in critically ill patients. Studies by K.M.Ho, K. Y. Lee et al showed that APACHE II score was a better predictor of mortality than SOFA score. [5] However, Q Qiao et al in their study observed that SOFA score was a better predictor of mortality than the APACHE II score in critically ill elderly patients. [6] In this study the APACHE II score and SOFA score of patients admitted with sepsis and MODS will be calculated and compared to determine their reliability as mortality predictors.

Objective:

To compare and determine the reliability of APACHE II and SOFA scoring system in predicting the clinical outcome in terms of mortality or survival in ICU patients with sepsis with MODS.

Materials and methods

Study Centre: medicine intensive care unit at a tertiary care center. Duration of study: 6 months

Study Design: observational study (prospective)
Sample size: 60 patients

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients above 18 years of age.
2. Patients with evidence of sepsis and mods on admission.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients being treated with immunosuppressant medications
2. Patients having retroviral infection
3. Ante natal patients

Data collection and methods
Patients are subjected to history taking; clinical examination and relevant laboratory investigations are done. Patients admitted with sepsis and mods are selected for clinical study as per inclusion / exclusion criteria. History regarding the clinical presentation, comorbidities is recorded.

After thorough clinical examination they are subjected to routine blood tests like complete hemogram, renal function tests, serum electrolytes, liver function test and arterial blood gas analysis.

Use of any inotropes, ventilatory support, dialytic interventions if any was noted for including in the sofa score. Apache ii score was calculated within the first 24 hours. Sofa score is calculated on day 1 and 3 and the mean sofa score is calculated.

Statistical analysis and methods-

Data was collected by using a structure proforma. Data thus was entered in MS excel sheet and analysed by using SPSS 24.0 version IBM USA. Qualitative data was expressed in terms of percentages and proportions.

Quantitative data was expressed in terms of Mean and Standard deviation. Association between two qualitative variables was seen by using Chi square/ Fischer's exact test. Descriptive statistics of each variable was presented in terms of Mean, standard deviation, standard error of mean.

A p value of <0.05 was considered as statistically significant whereas a p value <0.001 was considered as highly significant.

Table 1: Age wise distribution of survivors and non-survivors

Age group	Number of patients	Survived	Died	Mortality percentage
20 – 30	5	2	3	60%
30- 40	12	9	3	25%
40 – 50	10	5	5	50%
50 – 60	13	8	5	22.70%
60 – 70	13	11	2	38.50%
70 – 80	6	3	3	50%
> 80	1	0	1	100%

We included total 60 patients in our study. There were 13 cases each from 50-60- and 60-70- years age group followed by 12 from 30-40 years, 10 from 40-50 years, 6 from 70-80 years and 5 from 20-30 years age group. Death rate was highest in 20-30 years i.e. 60% followed by 50% from 40-50 years and 70-80 years each, 38.5% from 60-70 years, 25% from 30-40 years and 22.7% from 50-60 years age group.

Table 2: Gender wise distribution of survivors and non-survivors

Male			Female		
Total	Survived	Died	Total	Survived	Died
31	22	9	29	16	13

We included 31 males and 29 females in our study. Death rate in males was 29.03% and in females was 44.82%.

Table 3: APACHE II score and its correlation with mortality

Parameter	Survivors		Non-survivors		t	P
	Mean	Standard deviation	Mean	Standard deviation		
APACHE II Score	16.81	4.52	25.63	5.78	6.44	< 0.05

Mean APACHE II score in survivors was 16.81 ± 4.52 and in non survivors was 25.63 ± 5.78 . we compared the APACHE II score between two groups and found that the difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). P value is significant, implying that APACHE II score is a good and reliable predictor of mortality in patients admitted with sepsis – MODS.

Table 4: SOFA score and its correlation with mortality

Parameter	Survivors		Non-survivors		t	P
	Mean	Standard deviation	Mean	Mean		
Mean Sofa Score	5.63	1.9	11.38	1.66	11.55	< 0.05

Mean APACHE II score in survivors was 16.81 ± 4.52 and in non survivors was 25.63 ± 5.78 . We compared the APACHE II score between two groups and found that the difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). The p value was found to be significant. Hence a higher mean SOFA score indicates a higher probability of mortality.

Discussion

Treating patient and predicting mortality in the ICUs is always a challenge as well as great concern for physicians. The effect of this prediction is on various aspects of patient care, such as medical treatment, triage, end-of-life ICU care, and many more.

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in finding new prognostic markers like mNUTRIC score in critically ill ICU patients. Primary outcomes of this study were to compare mortality by different scoring system in critically ill patients. Secondary outcome was to analyse the need of mechanical ventilation and length of ICU stays which may have affected mortality. Most of the time because of variable institutional and population parameters, ICU mortality rates also varies which ranges from 6.4 to 46%. [7,8]

In our study, mortality rate was 14.7% in less than 50 years of age, 20.7% among 50–75 years of age, and 42.0% in older than 75 years of age. Study by Leong and Tai and Ursavaş et al. had not shown any direct relation as far as increasing age and mortality rates are concerned. They further quoted that age was not a deciding factor in a ICU patient. [7,8,9]

Kumar S. et al [10] reported that the estimated mortality by APACHE-II score was 46.47 ± 22.81%, 56.43 ± 20.21%, 64.04 ± 20.46% (p value < 0.0011) in the same groups, respectively. In this study, we had found trend of increase in APACHE II scores and mortality as patient's age increases.

On comparing different scoring system with mortality, APACHE-II and SOFA had better sensitivity and

specificity than mNUTRIC Score, which had high sensitivity but low specificity. Same observation was in case of need for mechanical ventilation. In this study, there was a weak positive correlation between APACHE-II score and SOFA score with ICU length of stay but moderate positive correlation with mNUTRIC score.

Conclusion

- Both the APACHE II score and SOFA scores were noted to have significant correlation with mortality in cases of sepsis – multi organ dysfunction syndrome.
- Higher values of APACHE 2, SOFA scores were associated with higher mortality
- A serial monitoring of SOFA scores on consecutive days is a better prognostication tool than a single value. A rising SOFA score on subsequent days is likely to be associated with higher mortality risk.

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